

THE ROLE OF THE WORK CARRIED OUT IN THE SYSTEM OF PRESCHOOL EDUCATION IN UZBEKISTAN

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Annotation: This thesis aims to highlight the latest work done in the preschool education system, in particular, the English language program and various implemented activities.

Introduction: One of the main things that should be done for the further development of education is the development of textbooks, programs, training manuals, etc. that meet the requirements of the current time. First of all, textbooks or programs should provide knowledge to children and, in addition, should have great educational value. In recent years, there has been a reformation of textbooks and study guides in almost all educational systems. In addition, it can be said that various activities, including increasing knowledge, electronic library, or foreign cooperation for the development of education are making a big turn in preschool education.

Main body: In 2022, a lot of work was carried out in the preschool education system to develop foreign languages, including the development of a program for teaching foreign languages in accordance with state educational standards. We actively participated in the creation of this program. The introductory part of the program is covered with the content, tasks, activities, etc. of the program. The basis of the program is the thematic plans aimed at teaching foreign languages. After the thematic plans, an activity plan for the teacher was drawn up.

The main principles of didactics, children's age and psychophysiological characteristics were taken into account in the distribution of program sections. The content of the program consists of topics that allow you to change the training within the topic. This includes English situations, language materials, speaking skills. The main tasks of the program are as follows (Table 1):

Tasks of the program	Developing children's interest in the English language, the desire to speak English, listening to songs, English speech, watching English cartoons, organizing a pedagogical process based on the child's favorite activity (play, productive activity).
	Preparing children for the process of language learning and familiarizing them with topics: talking about the role of a foreign language in human life.
	Develop listening skills by listening to speech containing basic vocabulary familiar to children.
	To prepare for staging a fairy tale together with children, to understand the speech addressed to them during the execution of the program, and to develop the skills of responding appropriately to appeals using appropriate replication situations in a role-playing game.
	To introduce children to well-known parts of the language being studied.
	Introducing children to the fairy tales of the country of the language being studied.

In addition, the program includes the activities of children and teachers in the educational process. We can see the forms of this process in the following picture (Figure 2):

The program is aimed at forming various foreign language skills of children during the educational process (Figure-3):

In 2022, the Ministry of Pre-school Education has also done great work in addition to those mentioned above. For example, the order of the Minister of Pre-School Education dated March 25, 2022 No. 67 on the theme “Nature in the eyes of children” on the organization of a Republican exhibition dedicated to and in honor of the competition of pictures of preschool children done. Also, pupils of preschool educational organizations and students of general educational institutions of our country participated in the picture competition on the theme “Peace on Earth - in our hands”, presented materials were displayed at the exhibition, and from May 30 to June 2 the exhibition was shown at the Palace of Youth Creativity.

In accordance with the “Regulation on holding chess competitions among students of preschool educational organizations”, the chess competition “Uzbekistan’s first” among students of preschool educational organizations was organized step by step: organizations , district (city), region and republic. In addition, this year, the Ministry provided teaching-methodical and didactic materials to state, non-state and family preschool education organizations based on the Decision PD-5144 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

In order to develop foreign languages, the Ministry of Preschool Education together with the Greek publishing house “MM-publication” launched “Hi Kids!” The book “For Uzbekistan” was presented to educational organizations, and seminar trainings on this book were held. In

addition, specialists of the Ministry of Preschool Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan, UNICEF and the Innovation Center of Information and Pedagogical Technologies “Bilim Makon” jointly created a digital platform called “Childhood Academy” (www.bolakadem.uz).

Conclusion: In conclusion, it should be said that education always requires changes, that is, the country will develop and progress only if innovations are regularly made in the field.

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